

MAP OF PHASE 2B
CLINICAL TRIAL
SITE COUNTRIES

VISION-DMD IS AN INTERNATIONAL COLLABORATION BETWEEN RESEARCH INSTITUTIONS, CLINICIANS, UNIVERSITIES, PHARMA INDUSTRY, PATIENT GROUPS AND SMES

CERATIUM
helping research happen

ReveraGen
BioPharma

This consortium builds new partnerships with existing neuromuscular clinical trial network resources and experts in drug development

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**PHASE 2 CLINICAL TRIALS
OF VAMOROLONE:**

An Innovative Steroid-like Intervention on
Duchenne Muscular Dystrophy

Learn more at
www.vision-dmd.info

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ABOUT DUCHENNE MUSCULAR DYSTROPHY (DMD)

DMD is a very severe rare disease affecting 1 : 5000 male births with onset usually between 2 and 4 years of age. DMD is caused by mutation in the dystrophin gene for the production of the protein dystrophin. It is a progressive disorder, muscles progressively weaken and eventually stop working, causing related issues including cardiac and respiratory problems.

There is currently no cure for DMD.

VENTURE PHILANTHROPY

VISION-DMD is a patient group and academic researcher driven project, with funding for drug development being focused on innovative venture philanthropy through patient group funding and public investment.

The VISION-DMD project will be a model for affordable rare disease drug development providing an affordable business model and lower drug costs.

THE PROJECT

VISION-DMD aims to advance the clinical development of the orphan drug vamorolone, an innovative steroid-like drug designed to retain or improve glucocorticoids efficacy and improve membrane stabilization with reduced side effects, as a new therapy for all patients with Duchenne Muscular Dystrophy.

VAMOROLONE: AN INNOVATIVE STEROID-LIKE INTERVENTION FOR DMD

Vamorolone (also known as VBP15) has received Orphan Drug Designation in the US and Europe for the treatment of DMD. Vamorolone, is being developed by ReveraGen Biopharma. The drug is a dissociative steroid designed to try to enhance the good features delivering efficacy (clinical benefit) and reduce or remove the bad features causing side effects and safety concerns. ReveraGen is also developing vamorolone for other indications.

About 50% of DMD patients are currently prescribed daily glucocorticoids. The goals of steroid treatment are to slow disease progression, control secondary conditions and to improve the quality of life of the patients. Unfortunately side effects currently prevent long term prescription of glucocorticoids.

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AN INNOVATIVE STEROID-LIKE DRUG

TARGETING AN UNMET NEED

The project will undertake research on a number of innovative outcome measures assessing feasibility and clinical relevance for use in future clinical trials including:

Exploratory pharmacodynamic biomarkers for clinical safety and clinical efficacy.

Novel bone study to assess changes in bone over time.

Mobile Health Band study investigating the feasibility of wearable healthcare technology for recording activity data.

Innovative consenting/assenting patient information APP designed to provide information to young children about the clinical trial.

Utilise a novel Venture Philanthropy model to derisk the development.

VISION-DMD CLINICAL TRIALS

PHASE 2A CLINICAL STUDY

To assess safety and dose finding
Study completed and results available
2a extension study complete
Continued study drug access through long term extension study

PHASE 2B CLINICAL STUDY

To evaluate the safety, efficacy and tolerability of vamorolone
First trial sites opened August 2018
120 ambulant steroid naïve DMD boys aged 4-7 years
Over 30 trial sites in 11 countries (USA, Canada, UK, Israel, Australia, Sweden, Spain, Greece, Netherlands, Czech Republic and Belgium)

VAMOROLONE DEVELOPMENT HAS BEEN SUPPORTED BY:

